

N-N'-Di (Thiocarbamoyl) Hydrazin and its Derivatives as Analytical Reagents: X. Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt with Dalzin*

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Cobalt dalzinate has been shown to be soluble in pyridine and alkylamines forming green and red solutions. Tentative structures for both the green and red varieties have been proposed. The green solution in pyridine has been used for the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt.

Like other bivalent metals cobalt has been found¹ to be quantitatively precipitated as a black compound at pH 7-8 with Dalzin. Dalzin has also been used for the spectrophotometric determinations of bismuth² and palladium.³ Cobalt dalzinate (CoDal) has been found soluble in pyridine and primary amines forming coloured solution which is quite stable and is thus found suitable for its colorimetric determination. This paper describes the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt with Dalzin in pyridine medium.

The solubility of cobalt dalzinate in various organic solvents can be summarised as follows: the black cobalt complex is insoluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, benzene, toluene, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride; slightly soluble in ethylacetate but moderately soluble in pyridine and alcohol mixture giving a bright green solution and in primary alkylamines giving red solutions:

Reagent	Colour	Extractibility
Cobalt a. Py + Alc	Green	Extractible with ethylacetate in presence of some water to form a green solution
b. Methylamine + Alc	Red	Extractible; solution green ⁴
c. Py + NH ₂ OH + Alc	Pink	Extractible; solution green ⁵
d. Dimethylamine + Alc	Dirty green	Ethylacetate; extract green.
e. Tertiary amine	Dirty green; solution turbid.	

At first, the green coloured solution was supposed to be due to Co (III) complex and the pink in presence of hydroxylamine as that of Co (II) complex. But all the solutions and the solids separated from them and the original black cobalt dalzinate weighed as such in the gravimetric determinations were found to be paramagnetic. These observations have been explained by the following tentative reactions:

*Taken out from a part of D.Phil. thesis of P. K. De.

1. P. K. De, *Ind. J. Appl. Chem.*, 1965, 28, 66.

2. Gupta and Sen Sarma, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 29, 29.

3. N. K. Dutt and K. P. Sen Sarma, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 39, 1.

Much of the alkylamine is removed in the aqueous layer (*cf.* Reaction C $\rightarrow$ D). The green solution in ethyl acetate is converted back into red by addition of more alkylamine. When only limited amount of alkylamine is used, the green variety is formed.

A + 2 or 3 moles RNH₂ $\rightarrow$ Green solution (*cf.* D).

Similarly, the complex with pyridine in presence of hydroxylamine may have a structure, like C with 2NH₂OH and 2 pyridine (E). This on extraction with ethylacetate gives a green solution with structure like B having 2 pyridine or less likely 2NH₂OH. This green solution does not change colour with more pyridine indicating the former as a more probable structure. Composition of green variety has been studied by Job's method (*vide infra*) and has always been found to have 1:1 cobalt-dalzin ratio.

The green ethyl acetate extracts on evaporation and washing several times with 75% alcohol always left black residues which on analysis corresponded to CoDal H₂O (N, 18.5%) indicating that the ligands are only loosely bound to the CoDal molecule.

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus.—A Hilger Uvispek Spectrophotometer was employed for making absorbance measurements. pH measurements were carried out with Cambridge bench type pH-meter using glass electrode.

Materials.—Standard cobalt solution was prepared by dissolving nickel-free cobalt salt (G. R. E. Merck quality) in distilled water. The cobalt content of this solution was determined by the sulphate method. Dalzin solution [0.1% (w/v) in absolute alcohol was used. Freshly twice distilled pyridine collected between 115-116°C was used. Potassium cyanide solution (1% aqueous solution) (Extra Pure E. Merck) was used. Other solutions required were all prepared from (G. R. E. Merck) chemicals.

Colour reaction.—In alkaline medium, Dalzin in presence of pyridine and alcohol reacts instantaneously with cobalt giving a green solution; the same reaction with methylamino produces a red colour. The green system having larger optical densities than the red system has subsequently been used.

A study of the absorption curve of the green cobalt complex from 350 $m\mu$ to 600 $m\mu$ reveals no absorption maxima. The working portion of the curve is shown in Fig. 1. The absorption of the complex read against the reagent blank decreases steadily as the wavelength increases. The reagent blank shows no absorption in this region. Preferring the work in the visible region and considering moderate values of O.D.'s, any wavelength between 370 $m\mu$ -400 $m\mu$ appears to be more suitable. Because the decrease in absorption is practically the same (for different solutions) from 380-460 $m\mu$, all subsequent measurements were made at 390 $m\mu$.

For comparison, absorption curves produced with methylamine, dimethylamine and pyridine-hydroxylamine are also shown in Fig. 2.

Effect of Concentration of Pyridine, Alcohol and Reagent.—The amount of pyridine can be varied from 2-4 ml. in a volume of 25 ml. and reagent added subsequently for colour development. The concentration of alcohol does not affect the intensity of colour. However, it should not go below 50%. Usually, 2 ml. of 0.1% reagent is sufficient for 1-20 p.p.m. of Co in a volume of 25 ml.

Effect of pH, Time and Temperature.—Fig. 3 shows the optical densities at different pH values of a solution containing 5 p.p.m. Co and 2 ml. pyridine in a final volume of 25 ml. measured against a suitable reagent blank. The pH adjustments were made with the help

of a pH meter and by using dilute hydrochloric acid or ammonia. Results obtained show that maximum colour intensity develops at pH 6.7 and remains stable up to pH 11.

FIG. 3

The green colour developed with 5 p.p.m. of Co and 2 ml. pyridine and 1 ml. reagent in 25 ml. is quite stable for 24 hr. Even with larger quantities no opalescence appears but colour usually gradually fades out after that period. The colour has been found to be stable between 25° to 40°.

Beer's Law and Sensitivity.—The colour intensity has been found to be proportional to the cobalt concentration. It obeys Beer's law for concentrations ranging from 1 p.p.m. to 10 p.p.m. which is evident from the fact that straight lines passing through the origin are obtained when the optical densities at different wavelengths are plotted against the respective concentrations (Fig. 4). The sensitivity of the colour reaction is 0.020 Co per cm^2 at 380 $\text{m}\mu$ and 0.025 at 390 $\text{m}\mu$ respectively.

Procedure.—To an aliquot quantity of a standard cobalt solution is added 2 ml. of pyridine, 2 ml. of the reagent solution and is then made up to volume (25 ml.) with 75% alcohol (pH=8.3). As the pH range is wide (8.7-11) no special precaution is necessary to maintain pH. After thorough mixing, a portion of the solution is transferred to a 1 cm absorption cell and the optical density is measured against a blank containing the same solution without cobalt.

Effect of Foreign Ions.—Since Dalzin forms complexes with a number of metal ions, interferences occur when they are present. These interferences, however, may be eliminated by use of suitable complexing agents. Thus with thiourea, small amounts of Cu^{+2} and Ag^+

are made harmless. Potassium cyanide suppresses the absorption of nickel complex completely. Sodium fluoride will prevent iron to develop a yellow colour or turbidity with pyridine, while cobalt colour is unaffected.

Effect of Potassium Cyanide.—It has been found that on addition of KCN solution, the green colour changes to pink. The absorption curve of this pink follows the same course of that of the other pink solution although they have less absorbances. An excess of potassium cyanide does not further alter the cobalt colour intensity. The new system was found to obey Beer's law (Fig. 5). The colour is developed as before, and 1 ml. of 1% KCN solution is added before making up volume. The absorbances are then measured at 380 m μ and 390 m μ .

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

Determination of Cobalt in presence of Nickel.—The golden yellow colour of nickel with dalzin and pyridine is completely discharged on treatment with KCN. This has made it possible to determine cobalt in presence of nickel by the addition of KCN. The solutions of Ni and Co are taken, colour is developed by reagent and pyridine, and then KCN solution added. It is essential that KCN solution is added only after the colour has developed, otherwise both Co and Ni will form stable cyano-complexes. Absorbances are then measured against a blank solution containing an equal amount of all reagents including nickel which shows practically no absorptions at these wavelengths (380 and 390 m μ).

The toleration limits of foreign ions (p.p.m.) for 3 p.p.m. Co are PO_4^{3-} , tartarate, citrate, acetate (100), fluoride (200), MoO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-} (100), Fe^{3+} (100 in presence of fluoride), Ag^+ (5) and Cu^{2+} (10 in presence of thiourea), Ni^{2+} (20 in presence of KCN). Bi^{3+} , Hg^{2+} , Pd^{2+} etc. interfere even when present in small amounts.

Composition of the Coloured Complex (Green): Job's method.—Two sets of solutions are prepared: (A) Cobalt+Py+alcohol, and (B) Reagent+Py+alcohol-solution being equimolecular (10^{-3}M) with respect to cobalt and reagent.

Varying proportions of two solutions in each set (keeping the total volume constant) are then mixed and optical densities measured against blanks containing py+alcohol+reagent.

Experiments are carried at several wavelengths between 380 to 400 μ (Fig. 6).

Observations lead definitely to the conclusion that the complex between cobalt and the reagent is formed when the reactants (Co and Dalzin) are in the ratio of 1 : 1 as in the black compound isolated from solution.